

Digitalization in Marketing

Mrs Sayli Sameer Bapat

Assistant Professor, Tilak Maharashtra Vidyapeeth, Pune, Maharashtra, India

ABSTRACT

The world has transitioned into a digital environment. For today's businesses, it is imperative to have a website and use the web as a means to interact with their customers. There are some successful traditional marketing strategies, particularly if you are reaching a largely local audience, but it is important to take advantage of digital marketing so as to keep up in today's world. Online Marketing uses internet to deliver promotional marketing messages.

Digital marketing is also known as Internet marketing, but their actual processes differ, as digital marketing is considered more targeted, measurable and interactive. It includes Internet marketing techniques, such as Display advertising, Web Banner advertising, pop ups, text ads, display ads, Social Media Marketing (SMM), Mobile Advertising, E-mail Advertising, Search Engine Optimization (SEO), Search Engine Marketing (SEM) and link building. It also extends to non-Internet channels that provide digital media, such as short messaging service (SMS), Multimedia Messaging Service (MMS), callback and on-hold mobile ring tones, e-books, optical disks and games.

KEYWORDS: *Digitalization of Marketing, Social Media Marketing, You Tube Marketing, Online Marketing, Online Shopping, Internet Marketing Platforms.*

INTRODUCTION

We live in an era where everything is interconnected. With the availability of anything and almost everything on a single click at your door step, advertising and marketing are not the same anymore. These days, it is important to have a strong online presence, along with a great brand that is presented

uniformly across all mediums. Digital Marketing is essential for companies who want to utilize the power of the internet in order to boost their business. Digital Marketing is also known as 'Online Marketing' 'Internet Marketing' or 'Web Marketing'.

Digitalization is the use of digital technologies to change a business model and provide new revenue and value-producing opportunities; it is the process of moving to a digital business. Digital marketing is the marketing of products and services using digital technologies, mainly on the internet, which also includes mobile phones, display advertising and any other digital medium.

In 1971, Ray Tomlinson sent the very first e-mail, and his technology set the platform to allow people to send and receive files through different machines. In 1990s, the term Digital Marketing was first coined, with the debut of server/client architecture and the popularity of personal computers, the Customer Relationship Management (CRM) applications became a significant part of marketing technology. In the 2000s, with more and more internet users and the birth of iPhone, before consulting a sales person, customers started searching products and making decisions about their needs online first which created a problem for the marketing companies as most of the retailers did not provide their domain address. In 2007, the concept of marketing automation was raised to solve the above mentioned problem. By 2010, digital marketing became sophisticated and was still growing till 2012-13. In 2000s, the development of social media sites such as Facebook, Youtube and Twitter made the customers highly dependent on digital electronics in their daily lives. The change of

Customer behavior improved the diversification of marketing technology.

Crossing the national and geographical boundaries, Digitalization in marketing has brought about tremendous changes in the methods of marketing, providing a wide access of potential customers. Due to digitalization in marketing it has become easy for the small and medium size business to advertise their business to a wide range of people as it is cheaper in cost as compared to the traditional marketing and advertising methods. It has also facilitated instant feedback from the customers. Lots of time and efforts are saved by making the website of the business where in the business can be made available 24/7 to the customers resulting in increased sales and profits. Staying connected with the customers by use of e-mails or multiple messages in a short span of time helps save the tedious task of sending newsletter to every client.

It allows two-way communication between a company and consumer in a way that wasn't previously seen and it has changed the business approach as the consumer holds more power now. It includes Internet marketing techniques, such as Display advertising, Web Banner advertising, pop ups, text ads, display ads, Social media marketing (SMM), Mobile advertising, e-mail advertising, search engine optimization (SEO), search engine marketing (SEM) and link building. It also extends to non-Internet channels that provide digital media, such as short messaging service (SMS), multimedia messaging service (MMS), callback and on-hold mobile ring tones, e-books, optical disks and games.

This research paper is based on the secondary data collected from various websites and describes the different types of digital marketing techniques like SEO, SEM, SMM, PPC, etc. Significance is given to the importance of digital marketing and its benefits. It aims to identify the effectiveness of Digital marketing. The objective is to identify the contribution of Online marketing in the changing marketing scenario and the reason for its growing popularity.

TOOLS OF DIGITAL MARKETING

A. Online Marketing

For any business to succeed, it is very important to reach out to consumers and establish the brand. Without a marketing solution a business cannot be

successful. Online marketing is a strategy that helps build a company's reputation and exposure online by using a variety of internet tools and solution. Before it is possible to understand the different strategies and marketing tools, it is important to understand what is online marketing and how it promotes business.

Online marketing which is also called internet marketing or online advertising is a tool strategy or a method of getting the company name out to the public. The advertisements can take many different forms and some strategic focus on some subtle messages rather than clear cut advertisements. But the way it promotes the business is simple. It builds up the company reputation by increasing its ability to be found online. A large number of potential customers browse the internet, look for information or simply enjoy their favorite past times with the internet connections. By taking advantage of the tools and resources, it is possible to get the company name out to the public and encourage potential customers to look further for information. Thus, online marketing or internet advertising or web advertising is a form of marketing and advertising which uses the internet platform to deliver promotional marketing messages to the consumers. So, Online Marketing is the practice of leveraging web-based channels to spread a message about a company's brand, products or services to its potential customers. The methods and techniques used for online marketing include e-mail, Social Media, Display Advertising, Search Engine Optimization and many more.

B. Search Engine Optimization (SEO)

After a website is built for the company, it needs promotion. Search Engine Marketing (SEM) is one of the best ways to promote your company, its services and its website. It is the process and strategy of getting website exposure online with keywords related to your business. This is called Search Engine Optimization (SEO). Search Engine Optimization (SEO) is the process of optimizing website content online to increase exposure in the organic search results for desired key words. This is a long term strategy that has many factors contributing to its success. These include, site architecture, on site content, off site content or on page and off page content. It also includes internal and external links, key word research and competition analysis to name a few. While being found online is probably the most important part of online marketing strategy, there are other types of marketing strategies that supplement

these efforts. SEO is the process of affecting the online visibility of a website or a webpage in a web search engines unpaid results – often referred to as natural, organic or earned results. It is the process of getting traffic from the free organic or natural search results on all search engines. All major search engines such as Google, Bing, and Yahoo have primary search results where web pages and other content such as videos or local listings are shown and ranked based on what the search engine considers the most relevant to users. Thus, it is the practice of increasing quantity and quality of traffic to your website through organic search results. It is done by improving rankings in the algorithmic search engine results.

C. Social Media Marketing

Social media is a collection of websites or applications that let people interact with each other by creating and sharing images, text, videos and even GIFs. There are a variety of social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Whatsapp, LinkedIn, Youtube, Instagram, Snapchat, etc. Social Media has completely changed the way a business can reach its customers. From small start ups to large corporates, companies are using social media to reach and inspire people all over the world. It offers a huge amount of opportunity to really get to know your customers and build relationships with them. It is an exciting way to do marketing and promotions and reach a wider audience for spreading information about you. Social Media isn't great just for personal use but it can also be a highly effective tool for any business. Companies of all sizes, as well as NGO's, or any person can use social media to connect with customers and grow their online community. Using Social Media to reach out to people and promote your business is known as social Media Marketing.

With Social Media, many successful businesses are changing the way people learn, explore and discover new things. It also allows businesses to advertise in a targeted, consumer-focused way, offering the potential for great value for money from advertising budgets. Social media marketing is a two way conversation where direct interaction helps create a stronger and a long lasting customer relationship. It's reactive nature means, communicating in a timely way which has never been simpler. It is an effective way to create business awareness and a positive, memorable impression. For e.g. Social Media Posts that encourage customers in engaging with the business. It allows businesses to engage, entertain and

respond to the audiences. Instead of talking with customers as with some traditional media, it lets you listen and respond to them in a personally tailored and immediate manner. This way of communicating with the new and existing customers can transform how a business promotes itself. A simple, open conversation can help people feel more at ease when interacting with you. It also helps improve marketing and customer retention and how it gives new audience insights that help sharpen your offerings.

So what's so great about Social Media Marketing is that, it has a lot of potential benefits for businesses.

- It helps you reach your new customers quickly.
- It offers a business the potential to reach millions of people all over the world in a targeted and personalized way.
- It gives you real time access
- It builds trust and relevance
- It allows you to build community

Therefore, we can say that social media marketing encourages a two way conversation. It gives you the opportunity to grow business by listening to and understanding your customer needs and preferences. Connecting via social media means people around the world can have conversations about you and your business and also share their experiences and recommend you to friends and family.

D. Display Advertising

Display advertising is an advertising on websites or apps or social media through banners or other advertising formats made of text, images, flash and audio- video. It is an online form of advertising that the company's promotional messages appear on third party sites or search engine results page such as publishers or social networks. It is a form of advertising that conveys a commercial message visually using text, logos, animations, videos, photographs or other graphics. Display advertising frequently target users with particular traits to increase the ads effect. It is a type of paid advertising also known as Pay-Per-Click Advertising or also called as PPC. It is a type of paid advertising that gets your business found on search engines. It is a great way to compete in the online space and directly target customers or consumers in your area for using a search engine to look for products or services. The beauty of this is that you have a chance to compete with the bigger competitors in local market without spending much money. It also gives small business

owners a way to directly target searchers based on their geography. So your search engine ads only show to people who are around your store or service area. It is like having a bill board online, but your targeting is much more effective because it is only being shown to people in the local area who are actually looking for your products and services. Pay-Per-Click is also known as Cost- Per- Click. It is an internet advertising model used to direct traffic to websites in which the advertiser pays the publisher when the ad is clicked. It is commonly associated with the first tier search engines. Essentially, it is a way of buying visits to your sites rather than attempting to earn those visits organically. Search Engine Advertising is one of the most forms of PPC. It is an online advertising model in which advertisers can display ads for their goods or services when users or people searching for things online enter relevant queries into the search engines. Advertisers are only charged when a user actually clicks on their ad and hence the name Pay-Per-Click or PPC.

It is a type of sponsored online advertising that is used for a wide range of websites including search engines where the advertiser only pays if a web user clicks on their ad. It works like a silent auction. Advertisers place bids on keywords or phrases that they think their target audience would type in a search field when they are looking for specific goods or services. When a web user types a search query into the field of search engine that matches the advertiser's key word list or visits a web page with content that co-relates to the key words or phrases chosen by the advertiser, the PPC ad may be displayed on the page. In a search engine, a PPC ad is generally just above or to the right side of the search results where they can be easily seen. On the other kind of web sites the ads will be placed in the location that the site designer has determined will be the most advantageous to his site and the advertiser. Overall PPC ads are beneficial to advertisers and web users alike. Advertisers get noticed by their target audience and are charged only for the times that their ads are clicked on and web users get to select from sites that may be relevant to the page that they are viewing without having to deal with obnoxious banner or pop-up ads that flash and distract.

E. You Tube Marketing

You Tube is a great source for funny, entertaining content, but it's also increasingly become an essential tool for marketers. In fact, nearly half of all marketers

plan to add You Tube marketing to their strategy every year. One third of all online activity is spent watching videos and You Tube has more than a billion active users today. The platform is so expansive that it can be accessed in 76 different languages, accounting for 95% of the world's population. It is considered to be internet's 2nd largest search engine and can help improve SEO and overall brand presence. You Tube allows marketers to present content in a unique way that is easy for viewers to consume and share. Unlike other social networking platforms you tube exclusively hosts video content. You Tube is owned by Google, as a result, when you sign up for a Gmail account you will automatically have access to a You Tube account, a Google + account and much more. You Tube makes it incredibly simple for you and others to promote your video across other social networks. You Tube can do a lot for the businesses who utilize it correctly and consistently. Video is a huge platform today. It is dominating the world of marketing and if you aren't using video you will almost lose out certainly to your competition. With video ranking higher on all social platforms and performing well in ads, customers are more likely to notice and respond to businesses using video. When you are using you tube, you will have a whole library of videos. You can then, upload the video files natively to each platform. You can also embed You Tube videos in your blog posts with just a few clicks, making your blog posts more dynamic and engaging. You Tube also has an enormous and very diverse audience which happily uses both you tube and Google search engine to find content that they are looking for. If you are able to optimize for the right key words, you will be able to connect with that audience instantly. Since you tube videos can show up early on in Google's search results, it is the second most commonly used search engine after Google. You Tube has really a very large and diverse audience. It has over a billion active users and the site gets over 30 million visitors every single day and you tubes audience watches more than 3.5 billion hours of video every month and more than 1 billion video views every day. Thus, you tube has become one of the most sought after online marketing platforms today. For any business to reach out to its audience you tube cannot be ignored.

F. Email Marketing

Email Marketing is basically the use of email to promote products and/or services. But a better email marketing definition is the use of email to develop

relationships with potential customers and/or clients. Email marketing is one segment of internet marketing, which encompasses online marketing via websites, social media, blogs, etc. It is essentially the same as direct mail except that instead of sending mail through the postal service, messages are sent electronically via email. Someone somewhere buys an email list (or several!) and sends an email along the lines of "Get _____ (the product name) for only Rs___! (amount) to everyone on the list—sometimes repeatedly. All this does is annoy everyone and give email marketing a bad name.

At its best, email marketing allows businesses to keep their customers informed and tailor their marketing messages to their customers.

Email Marketing Can Be Personalized

Particular groups of customers can be targeted or even individuals. Offering individual customers' special deals on merchandise and/or services on the customer's birthday, for instance, is one example of email marketing personalization. (A restaurant might send an email to customers on their birthday offering 50% off on entree.) Email marketing helps a business develop and maintain a relationship with a customer over time that hopefully results in increased sales and increased customer loyalty.

Email marketing best practices include developing your own email list rather than buying an email list(s) and making participation in your email list opt-in rather than opt-out (using permission-based email marketing). Email should also be optimized for mobile usage as according to statistics over half of emails are opened on mobile devices.

The Advantages of Email Marketing

The two big advantages of email marketing are price and ease. Emailing is an inexpensive way to advertise your company and its products and/or services compared to many other types of marketing. It's also extremely easy to set up and track an email marketing campaign, making it a very accessible type of marketing for small businesses.

Newsletters can be sent to the email list you've built from the people who provided the necessary information on your website, for instance, providing these potential customers with news updates about your company, upcoming events and/or special offers

– and, of course, reminding them that your business exists and that maybe it's time for another visit.

The huge advantage of email over social media is that prospects and customers are more likely to see an email than social media. Just posting something doesn't mean that everyone you want to see your message will see it. Your post might not even show up in your targets' social media streams. However, an email will sit in the inbox until its read (or deleted).

Ideally, email marketing should go hand-in-hand with social media. Adding social media "Like" or "Share" buttons to your marketing emails gives an additional way for customers to connect with your brand. Snippets of positive reviews from social media fans can be included in emails, and conversely, social media postings can be used to encourage fans to subscribe to your email newsletters.

Email marketing can substantially increase your income if you do it correctly. (See the tips below.) It's a great way to get people to visit and/or revisit your website or blog, and more traffic usually equates to more income.

Email Marketing Tips

1. Build your own list. This has already been mentioned but buying email lists is a waste of time. All you're going to do by sending unsolicited email is turn off most of the people you're hoping to turn into customers and run the risk of being labeled a spammer.
2. Adhere to the rules of the CAM-SPAM Act. These rules include having a non-deceptive subject line, a method of unsubscribing, and your name and address at the end of the emails.
3. Don't just send out ads to buy all the time. Use your emails to build rapport with customers by sharing your expertise and/or that of others, giving them tips and insights they can value. Share information that lets them know more about you and/or your company if it's interesting.
4. Treat your list well. Remember that the people you're using email to communicate with have trusted you with their email and name; they deserve your respect. Just as you deserve as a chance to convert them from customers to fans and even evangelists for your brand, people who want to talk about and share your message and get involved in any way they can.

5. Stick to a schedule if you're doing a newsletter. Sending email on a regular day or days can help your subscribers know what to expect from you and when. Also Known As: E-mail marketing, direct email marketing.

G. Mobile Marketing

Mobile marketing is a multi-channel, digital marketing strategy aimed at reaching a target audience on their smart phones, tablets, and/or other mobile devices, via websites, email, SMS and MMS, social media, and apps. Mobile is disrupting the way people engage with brands. Everything that can be done on a desktop computer is now available on a mobile device. From opening an email to visiting your website to reading your content, it's all accessible through a small mobile screen. 80% of Internet users own a Smartphone. Effective mobile advertising means understanding your mobile audience, designing content with mobile platforms in mind, and making strategic use of SMS/MMS marketing and mobile apps.

Mobile marketing is the art of marketing your business to appeal to mobile device users. When done right, mobile marketing provides customers or potential customers using Smartphone with personalized, time- and location-sensitive information so that they can get what they need exactly when they need it, even if they're on the go.

Mobile marketing consists of ads that appear on mobile smart phones, tablets, or other mobile devices. Mobile marketing ad formats, customization, and styles can vary, as many social media platforms, websites, and mobile apps offer their own unique and tailored mobile ad options.

Every business needs a mobile marketing strategy for the same reason that you need a computer and Wi-Fi access – this is the age in which we live! Walk around any major city and you'll find a lot of people with faces glued to their smart phone screens. According to recent reports, 40% of users' internet time is spent on mobile devices, which means simply ignoring the rise of mobile just isn't an option.

Types of Mobile Marketing Strategies

There's a healthy variety of mobile marketing strategies to try. The kind that works best for your business will depend on your industry, target audience, and budget.

App-based marketing: This is mobile advertising involving mobile apps. While 80% of mobile time is

spent engaged with apps, you don't have to create an app yourself to get in on the action. Services like Google Ad Mob help advertisers create mobile ads that appear within third-party mobile apps. Face book also allows advertisers to create ads that are integrated into Face book's mobile app. Face book's mobile Promoted Post ads integrate so seamlessly with Face book's news feed that users often don't realize they're looking at ads.

In game mobile marketing: In-game mobile marketing refers to mobile ads that appear within mobile games, like in the example below. In-game ads can appear as banner pop-ups, full-page image ads or even video ads that appear between loading screens.

QR codes: QR codes are scanned by users, who are then taken to a specific webpage that the QR code is attached to. QR codes are often aligned with mobile gamification and have an element of mystery to them, since users who scan them don't always know exactly which rabbit hole they're jumping down.

Location-based marketing: Location-based mobile ads are ads that appear on mobile devices based upon a user's location relative to a specific area or business. For example, some advertisers may only want their mobile ads to appear when users are within a 1-mile radius of their business.

Mobile search ads: These are basic Google search ads built for mobile, often featuring extra add-on extensions like click-to-call or maps.

Mobile image ads: Image-based ads designed to appear on mobile devices.

SMS: SMS marketing involves capturing a user's phone number and sending them text offers.

Conclusion

In comparison to the other mediums, digital marketing has proved to be more effective, given the need of the people in today's world as it is considered to be the most measurable. The different tools of digital marketing have made it easier and cheaper to advertise their businesses, products and services, though initially, the companies might have to bear higher costs. It has also made it easier to find potential customers and management of marketing campaigns. Being available to customers 24/7 so as to increase

the sales and profits is easily possible due to the digitalization in marketing.

There are various elements by which digital marketing is formed. All forms operate through electronic devices. Some of the elements have been explained through this research paper as trailing below:

Online Marketing is a very important part of digital marketing. It is also called as internet advertising through which a company can deliver the messages about products and services. Search Engine Optimization (SEO) is an organic way of maximizing the number of visitors to a particular website by ensuring that the website appears high in the search results returned by the search engine. Social Media Marketing is the use of social media sites as a platform to promote their businesses, products and services. Display advertising is advertising on websites or apps or social media through banners or other ad formats made of text, images, flash, video or audio. The main purpose of digital advertising is to deliver general advertisements and brand messages to site visitors. You Tube marketing is an essential strategy to take advantage of the web's massive shift towards video. E-mail marketing means sending a

commercial message typically to a group of people who could be potential customers or current or previous customers, using e-mail to build loyalty, trust or brand awareness. Mobile marketing is a multi-channel, digital marketing strategy aimed at reaching a target audience on their smart phones, tablets, and/or other mobile devices, via websites, emails, SMS and MMS, Social Media and apps.

Thus, we can conclude that digital marketing has no boundaries. It has become an essential part of marketing strategy of many companies. Digital marketing uses the power of internet and satisfies the demand of Business owners and customers in innovative ways.

References:

1. Elcom Blog
2. Wikipedia
3. www.inurture.co.in
4. www.worldstream.com
5. www.thebalancesmb.com
6. www.marketing-schools.warje
7. www.brickmarketing.com